

The trochoid differential equation

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The trochoid [1] has the parametric representation

$$(1) x = x(t) = at - b\sin(t)$$

$$(2) y = y(t) = a - b\cos(t) = dx/dt$$

To derive its differential equation, invoke the Chain Rule

$$y' = dy/dx = (dy/dt)(dt/dx) = (dy/dt)/(dx/dt)$$

so from (1) and (2)

$$y' = b\sin(t)/(a - b\cos(t)) = b\sin(t)/y$$

or

$$(3) yy'/b = \sin(t)$$

A reset of (2) gives

$$(4) (a - y)/b = \cos(t)$$

so 'square-and-add' of (3), (4) yields

$$(5) y^2(y'/b)^2 + (a - y)^2/b^2 = 1$$

Next, expansion of (5) leads to

$$(6) (y/b)^2 y'^2 + (a/b)^2 + (y/b)^2 - 2(a/b)(y/b) - 1 = 0$$

or

$$(7) (1 + y'^2)(y/b)^2 - 2(a/b)(y/b) + (a/b)^2 - 1 = 0$$

For notational simplicity let $z = y/b$ and $c = a/b$.

Eq. (7) becomes a quadratic in the z -variable:

$$(1 + y'^2)z^2 - 2cz + c^2 - 1 = 0$$

The (positive root) solution is

$$z = [c + \{c^2 - (1 + y'^2)(c^2 - 1)\}^{1/2}]/(1 + y'^2)$$

The curly bracket simplifies to

$$c^2 - (1 + y'^2)(c^2 - 1) = 1 - (cy')^2 + y'^2 = 1 + y'^2(1 - c^2)$$

so

$$z(1 + y'^2) = c + \{1 + y'^2(1 - c^2)\}^{1/2}$$

or, reverting back to the original variables

$$(y/b)(1 + y'^2) = (a/b) + \{1 + y'^2(1 - (a/b^2))\}^{1/2}$$

which simplifies to

$$y(1 + y'^2) = a + \{b^2(1 + y'^2) - a^2y'^2\}^{1/2}$$

Finally, the trochoid differential equation is:

$$(8) \quad y(1 + y'^2) - \{b^2(1 + y'^2) - a^2y'^2\}^{1/2} = a$$

For $a = b = R$, this reduces easily to

$$(9) \quad y(1 + y'^2) = 2R$$

the differential equation for the cycloid of radius R :

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= R(t - \sin(t)) \\ y(t) &= R(1 - \cos(t)) \end{aligned}$$

Reference

[1] Wikipedia article on the trochoid